

Hadeeth Mutawatir (Authentic Hadith)

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
July 03, 2020

Accepted:
August 04, 2020

Keywords

Hadeeth, Quran, Islam

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.4129969

Abstract

The sources of divine legislation for Muslims are: The Holy Quran and the "Sunnah" of the Prophet Mohammed (peace and blessings be upon him), that includes the hadiths of the Prophet Mohammed (peace and blessings be upon him), by word nor deed and his honorable biography. He inherited the Muslims from the Prophet Mohammed (peace and blessings be upon him), the noble "Sunnah", which is an explanation and a clear indication of the Holy Quran. Allah has revealed the Qur'an to the Prophet Mohammed (peace and blessings be upon him), and the Prophet clear and explained it to all the people. But the prophetic "Sunnah", especially the "Haadeeths", was exposed during the period of the Umayyad rule to sedition and the emergence of fraud and the situation and beyond to be distorted by corrupters. The Umayyad decrees have spent large sums of money so that the corrupters may put the weak of the souls in the hadiths to praise them, thus making the entry of a large number of false hadiths mixed with the correct "Hadeeth" from (Al-Hadeeth Al-mawdoo3). However, our righteous scholars put transmitting the prophetic tradition, authentic "hadeeth" and the atheists and divided the atheists to the right and the good and the weak and strong and classified the men of the modern and praise and ways to transfer to the other nothing remained in the "hadeeth" only they made it clear and classified it according to the type of "hadeeth". Allah rewarded them well for what they did to show the more authentic Hadeeth than others, The Quran is authentic in all ages since the revelation of God until this age, it is authentic and the terms of the authentic Hadeeth must be so, but we have reached a few of these impossible conditions that require hadeeth authentic.

1. Introduction

Because Transmitting the Prophetic Traditions one of the most powerful sciences, the most effective and most useful of all, for its connection with Allah and its messengers and successors, the Muslims - in the forefront of them the Imams of the Shiah - worked to codify it and then transfer it to the generations. Thus they laid down the rules of the Shari'a and Introduction (Aulia,2017).Because the science of modern science and the most closely linked and useful, to contact with God and his messengers and successors, the Muslims - and the forefront of the Shiite Imam - to codify and storage and then transferred to generations, and thus laid the rules of the law, and added the attribute of immortality and permanence and they recorded the science of Hadith to serve the "Sunnah" of the Prophet (Ayub,2018). First, write books about the strange and its dilemmas, and showed his problems and his instincts.

In authenticity

The authenticity in the language: is to follow the thing time after time with a period between them in the order or what came one after another in the order and the words of Allah (interpretation of the meaning): (44) "Then We sent Our messengers in succession .Every time there came to a nation its messenger,theydeniedhim,sowemadethemfollowoneanother[todestruction],andwemadethem narrations .So away with a people who do not believe "sura Al-Muminoon- Aya (44). (Tatar) is an authentic source and comes water from authenticity and its source is authentic. (Asfahani,1993)

Authentic term: It is the predicate (Khabr) or news of a group of self-stop come out of the certainty of the internal clues, which is not enough predicate (Khabr) or some of the external clues edge of the mews stuffed with the existence of the same. (IbnHajar,2010)

Shaykh al-Baha'i defined it as a chain in which each sect believes that it is not colluding with lying. It is authentic. Ibn Salah, who is a scholar of several centuries, referred to the authentic hadeeth: He wanted the verbal and apparent authenticity to be very mental authentic. (IbnManzoor,2004)

As for al-Suyuti, he referred to the hadiths that were set up in the time of the Umayyads in the case of their virtues and then became authentic and did not know that the scholars are considered the missing ones in terms of starting. From the "mobtada" subject to then it is the authentic "khabr" news that is transmitted by the person who receives the knowledge honestly and from the continuation of this condition in his narration from

the beginning to the end, the most prominent example of what is narrated from the hadeeth is the Prophet Mohammed (peace and blessings be upon him) said: (but works by intentions) (TheBabylonian,2004)

The truth is not authentic and that the shift in the number of authenticity and more because the authenticity got a new thing in the middle of his predicate and because Hadeeth uniqueness of his narrative (Omar bin Khattab) "God bless him" narrated it from the Messenger of Allah the Prophet Mohammed (peace and blessings be upon him) and then (Alqama) "God bless him" narrated it from him and then from Muhammad ibn Ibrahim on the authority of Alqama from him, Yahya ibn Sa'eed. This hadeeth is not authentic because he has lost one of the conditions of the authenticity, means in the beginning, as he warned him not one but spread the talk after Yahya bin Said more than 200 narrators (Al-Bukhari,2010)

The authentic news is the "khabr" predicate of a group benefit himself pieces honestly, that the saying (himself) what comes out is the certainty of the help of clues and evidence in two parts: the first internal clues which does not eliminate news about all or some of them, it is either related to the predicate adverb as being characterized by honesty and lack thereof or hears as a free-minded universe and not as a detective or as being close to be or not, or the same news as the bodies contained in the "khabr" predicate as a conclusion to the confirmation and oath and so on. (Baha'i,1976).

And the second is the external clues of the edge of the "khabr" predicate, and this is the so-called "khabr" predicate of the clues, as if "khabr" predicate came to the death of one and the clues to hear the cry from his house. This is useful to our knowledge of his validity of the restriction by saying (himself) to remove the second section of the "khabr" predicate, it is not useful for knowledge itself, but with clues. (Baha'i,1993)

It is noted on this definition that it is not consistent to be true to what is not authentic, as if he told three of the incident of the departure of the reasons for deliberately lying in it and the observation of the status of informants and the mind of the hearer of suspicion is required to be such an authentic news and not necessarily (Al-Jaafar,1979)

The "khabr" predicate of the group believes in their collusion to lie usually, but if the supplies more income in the benefit of that many science, what amounted to its narrations in abundance, an amount agreed to describe them in all classes where many narrated by some people until the first narrator will be the first in this description as the last and the middle as extremes to get the description. (Halit,2013) The impossibility of collusion to lie to the multiplicity in all classes of multiple and this should be authentic about many of the news that has reached its rudeness in our time that limit but did not agree in others, especially in the beginning and thought it was authentic (Ibnal-Hassan,1971).

In the possibility of learning and getting it

There is no doubt about the possibility of authentic news Al-Ghazali said: "The wise do not doubt that in this world, a town called Baghdad, although it does not enter it and there is no doubt about the existence of the prophets. This is what the ancients mentioned in the proof of its potential and its occurrence. Today we hear from the international media many scientific, social and political news, On the framework of the reasons for lying in it, and then that the investigator objected to the known infallibility means assertion of the existence of countries such as India, China and nations free as Pharaoh and the people of Moses that the science here is not the authenticity I hear only from the people of our time and they did not narrate us from their predecessor originally, As well as many gets by the authenticity and so on, but to know the hand that the people of the era are unanimous on that whole, either the statement or the emergence of their silence based on the non-nullification of this transfer (Hakim,1971).

If we find the people of our time agree on the news frank or commitment to happen in the past time, we may cut as an observation habit in that incident that agree on this is nothing but an agreement like the news until the end of the series to viewers, which we usually follow in that incident reach the frequency So we know the incident based on the late authenticity revealing the frequency of the advanced known to us by Hassan (Hakim,2005)

How to learn about the authenticity

1. If it was theoretically to stop on the mediation of the two offerings and the Almtafm we know the knowledge of the end of the authenticity such as the existence of Mecca and India and others with the absence of that. (UmmaFarida,2017)
2. If theoretically I did not get to those who can't look like the old men and boys.
3. If it was theoretically necessary not to let him deliberately leave the eyes if all theoretical knowledge, the world finds himself first hesitate and then ask and we find ourselves asking for the existence of Mecca (Al-Khatib,2000)

Al-Ghazali said: If you are interested in the theory that the mere statement of the informer to disperse science unless there are two introductions:

- First them: that those with different conditions and the contrast of their purposes and with many of them on the case does not gather them to lie collector and do not agree not to honesty (Al-Sobhani,2005)

• Secondly: They agreed on the news about the incident, so the science of truthfulness depends on the sum of the two offerings. This is a Muslim, and it is necessary for the soul to feel these two things so that it can receive the knowledge and the ratification, even if it does not make up these introductions in a systematic manner. (Hajer,2018) On the knowledge is the second introduction is their agreement to tell about this incident or the first introduction I mean no to collect them lying collector is the result or in the order of the flag does not stop them and not just the possibility of writing a measure produces the required angel because the result is theoretical, But it is possible to write in all necessary as our saying (all includes the part and increase) (Al-Saleh,1960)

The point is that the balance in the fact that science is necessary or theoretical is the need for the issue to be thorough and accurate and thought and consideration and evidence and what happens after the news quickly, although based on the issues of Islam in mind without borrowing and relying on it is necessarily aware. (Al-Sadr,2010).

In the conditions of the authentic

Section (1): here the opinion of the owners stated the conditions are:

- The fact that the informants are too old to refrain from associating them with lies, and it is said that it is not sufficient, but it is necessary to add to it the saying ("He believes in the intention of lying with them"), as if they were saying one thing and they were different,
- The fact that their knowledge is based on the good is that in the case of the occurrence of knowledge is certainly not useful for the large number of suspected theoretical issues. (Tibi,2002)
- The two sides are equal and the center means that each of the layers reaches the limit of the mass, so if there is more than one layer, otherwise there is no middle or multiple classes.
- The fact that he told them about knowledge, but if he told the people of Baghdad about a bird, they thought that he was a pigeon or that he was a zaid. this is not an explanation, but the case of the informant does not exceed that of the hearer.(ZineElAbidine,2002)

Section (2): What is the condition for obtaining knowledge from them and they said that it is stipulated that the hearer is not aware of what he has been told about the impossibility of collecting it, and it is stipulated that he should not have been suspected or imitated prior to the belief of the negation of what is mentioned by al-Murtada. The denial of knowledge of the authenticity of the miracles of the Prophet Mohammed (peace and blessings be upon him), and the text on the guardian, this is contrary to what is required by the authentic does not get him the flag with the abandonment of what he did about it only rarely (Al-Amali,1993)

The lowest number of authentic

They differed in the lowest number with which the authenticity and the right are achieved. There is no requirement for a number. The criterion is to inform a group that believes in their intention to lie. It differs and is lagging according to the different resources. There is enough resource in it if the subject is far from the hobby and lying. The question is not sufficient. Or twenty or forty or seventy basis is not based on the judge Abu Bakr al-Baqlani: It is required to be of four not to report the news of the four true toad with science, as is the case in the evidence of adultery and others stop in the five not to go to the evidence mentioned therein and Alastkhri that the lowest number in Because it is said that the number of the captives of the sons of Israel is as it says (12)And Allah had already taken a covenant from the Children of Israel, and We delegated from among them twelve leaders. "sura (Al-Maaida- Aya (12). and from Abu Hazael al-'Alaf, the lowest number is the twenty, because Allah says: *O prophet, urge the believers to battle. If there are among you twenty [who are] steadfast, they will overcome two hundred.*" sura (Al-Anfal- Aya (65). The knowledge of what they are told and it is said that the lowest number is the forty for Som Allah says: " *O Prophet, sufficient for you is Allah and for whoever follows you of the believers.*"sura (Al-Anfal- Aya (64). As it was revealed in the forty, it was said that the lowest number is the seventy, because Allah says: "And Moses chose from his people seventy men for Our Appointment" (Al-A3raf- Aya (155). The owners of what they see miracles and it was said that at least three hundred and a b Only ten per share was told the number of the people of Badr (OmarReza,1959). The authentic word is what the authenticity of the word as The Holy Qua'n and some of the words of the faithful and the master of worshipers Ali bin al-Hussein peace be upon them and the authentic verbal is Marawah word of collection about the collection does not fancy collusion on the lie from the beginning to the end of the speech. (Baqer,2009).As for the Hadeeth, moral discourse, it is the talk that is conveyed by all mentioned in different words and many methods or narrated in many Hadeeths with different meanings and different topics, all of which have a common meaning or that one meaning is common meaning. (Al-Maqamani,2008)

As for the authentic word and meaning, it is a combination of authentic words of the meaning and example, some of the verses of The Holy Qur'an, which agreed the novels of the people of Islam in its meaning and did not differ and reached the limit of authenticity as saying Almighty in denoting the negation of opposites and Synonyms (Nazad,2002).

Results

1. The science of Hadeeth is specialized in the Hadeeth and study of the Prophet Mohammed (peace and blessings be upon him) is an important science the intention for all Muslims, as he explained and shows the truth of the modern Suqaim talk as it builds the men and their qualities and origins and the location of the wound and amendment.
2. Authentic talk is one of the sources Islamic legislation on which Muslims depend on his health and honesty so scientists are interested in it a lot.
3. Hadiths prophetic authentic Muslims are rare and few of the difficulty of their terms authentic talk in which these conditions are very rare.
4. The Prophet's Hadiths, whose origins are a single story and then spread in a layer of its layers, became authentic as modern (but works by intentions). It is of the same origin and spread in the three layer of the Hadith. Many of the atheists spread in a class after the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him).
5. Despite all the conditions of the authentic Hadeeth is impossible to implement and apply, but the schools of imams peace be upon them have achieved this school Imam Al-Sadiq, which quoted us a number of authentic Hadiths.

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